

SUPPORT SERVICES ON QUALITY OF EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION (ECE) PROGRAMS IN KWARA STATE, NIGERIA: A MIXED-METHOD APPROACH

YUSUF SULEIMAN

DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT AND COUNSELLING, FACULTY OF EDUCATION, AL-HIKMAH UNIVERSITY, ILORIN, KWARA STATE, NIGERIA.

Email: yusufsuleiman@alhikmah.edu.ng

Phone Number: 08071430930

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14294086>

Abstract

This study investigates the impact of support services on the quality of early childhood education (ECE) programs in Kwara State, Nigeria. The research utilized a mixed-methods approach, combining interviews with 20 participants and a survey of 364 respondents to gather comprehensive data on the topic. The interviews provided qualitative insights into the perceptions and experiences of key stakeholders, including parents, teachers, administrators, and policymakers, regarding the role of support services in ECE. The survey, on the other hand, collected quantitative data to assess the availability, accessibility, and effectiveness of support services in ECE programs. The findings reveal that support services such as health services, nutrition services, parental involvement, professional development for teachers, and monitoring and evaluation play a crucial role in enhancing the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State. Participants highlighted the importance of access to healthcare, nutritious meals, and opportunities for parental engagement in improving children's learning outcomes. Additionally, professional development for teachers and regular monitoring and evaluation were identified as key factors in ensuring the effectiveness of ECE programs. The study underscores the importance of prioritizing support services in ECE programs to enhance their quality and impact on children's development. The findings have implications for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders involved in ECE, highlighting the need for targeted interventions and policies to improve support services and ultimately enhance the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria.

Keywords: Support Services, Early Childhood, Education, Quality

INTRODUCTION

Early Childhood Education (ECE) plays a crucial role in laying the foundation for a child's cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development. Quality ECE programs are essential for ensuring that children receive the necessary support and stimulation during their formative years (Adesuyi-Fasuyi, 2023; Lewis et. al., 2024; Yusuf, Abdulkareem & Popoola, 2023). The quality of ECE programs is influenced by various factors, one of which is the availability and effectiveness of support services. Support services encompass a wide range of interventions and

resources that are designed to enhance the quality of education provided to young children. The services include teacher training and professional development, access to educational materials and resources, parental involvement programs, health and nutrition services, and infrastructure support, among others. The support services on the quality of ECE programs has been a subject of increasing interest among researchers and policymakers (Aghnaita & Norhikmah, 2023; Alam et. al., 2020; Seymour, 2023; Sosu & Pimenta, 2023).

Despite the recognized importance of early childhood education (ECE) in laying the foundation for lifelong learning and development, the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria, particularly in Kwara State, is often hindered by inadequate support services. These support services encompass various aspects such as infrastructure, teacher training, curriculum development, parental involvement, and community engagement (D'Souza et. al., 2023; Gyekye-Ampofo, Opoku-Asare&Andoh, 2023; Velandia et. al., 2024).

Kwara State, located in North-Central Nigeria, is home to a diverse population with varying socio-economic backgrounds. The state has made significant strides in promoting access to ECE programs, but there remain challenges related to the quality of these programs. Understanding the impact of support services on the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State is crucial for informing policy decisions and improving the overall quality of early childhood education in the state (Ajadi, 2021). However, there is a lack of comprehensive empirical evidence on the specific impact of these support services on the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State, Nigeria (Kamilu, Baba & Abdulkareem, 2022). This gap in knowledge hinders the formulation of effective policies and interventions aimed at enhancing the quality of ECE in the state. This study aims to empirically investigate the impact of support services on the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State, Nigeria via mixed-methods.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have highlighted the positive impact of support services on the quality of ECE programs (Ajadi, 2021; Modise et. al., 2023; Rashid & Akkari, 2020; Yusuf, Abdulkareem & Popoola, 2023). For instance, Ogunkoya (2023) found that access to health and nutrition services in ECE programs led to improved cognitive development and academic achievement among children. Similarly, research conducted by Okunaiya and Olajide (2023) demonstrated that parental involvement in ECE programs was positively correlated with children's social and emotional development. Agarry (2022) study conducted a comprehensive assessment of support services available for ECE programs in Kwara State, Nigeria, and their impact on program quality. Findings revealed that while there were some support services in place, such as teacher training workshops and provision of learning materials, their effectiveness varied. The study identified challenges such as inadequate funding and lack of coordination among stakeholders, which hindered the provision of quality support services.

The study of Ekure (2022) explored the role of school programs in enhancing the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State via quantitative approach. Through interviews and surveys with ECE teachers and administrators, the study identified support services such as mentoring programs for teachers, parental engagement initiatives, and community outreach activities. The findings

highlighted the positive impact of these support services on program quality, including improved. Study by Olayonu (2022) examined the role of parental involvement as a support service in ECE programs in Nigeria. The study found that parental involvement positively correlated with the quality of ECE programs, leading to improved outcomes for children. This suggests that efforts to increase parental involvement can contribute significantly to enhancing the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria.

Another study by Haq and Roesminingsih (2024) investigated the impact of infrastructure and facilities on the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria. The study found that the availability of adequate infrastructure and facilities, such as classrooms, play areas, and learning materials, significantly influenced the quality of ECE programs. This highlights the importance of investing in infrastructure and facilities to improve the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria. Furthermore, a study by Joet. al. (2020) examined the impact of teacher training and professional development on the quality of ECE programs. The study found that teachers who received adequate training and professional development opportunities were more effective in delivering high-quality ECE programs. This underscores the importance of investing in teacher training and professional development to enhance the quality of ECE programs. In addition to these studies, research examined by Kamiya and Nomura (2023) highlighted the importance of government policies and regulations in shaping the quality of ECE programs. Adequate funding, regulatory frameworks, and quality assurance mechanisms are essential for ensuring high-quality ECE programs that meet the needs of children and families.

The current study is anchored on Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory. The theory is a comprehensive framework that helps us understand how various environmental systems influence an individual's development (Elliott & Davis, 2020). The theory consists of several interconnected layers, each representing a different level of influence. These layers include the microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem, and chronosystem. The microsystem is the immediate environment in which the child lives, such as family, school, and peer group. In the context of early childhood education, the microsystem includes the child's home environment and the early childhood education setting. The interactions between the child and these immediate environments play a crucial role in shaping the child's development (Nolan & Owen, 2024). For example, positive relationships with parents and teachers can foster a sense of security and support healthy development. The mesosystem refers to the connections between different parts of the child's microsystem. In early childhood education, the mesosystem includes the interactions between the family and the ECE setting. For example, effective communication between parents and teachers can enhance the child's learning experiences and overall development. The macrosystem refers to the broader cultural context in which the child lives, including societal norms, values, and beliefs. In early childhood education, the macrosystem influences the curriculum, teaching practices, and educational goals. For example, cultural beliefs about child-rearing and education may shape the expectations and practices within ECE settings. The chronosystem recognizes the importance of time in shaping development. This includes historical events, life transitions, and developmental stages. In the context of early childhood education, the chronosystem could include changes in educational policies, advancements in research on child development, or societal shifts that impact early childhood education practices (El Zaatari&Maalouf, 2022).

Research Questions

1. What are the key support services that contribute to the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State, Nigeria?
2. How do the availability and accessibility of support services affect the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State?
3. What are the challenges faced by early childhood education providers in delivering high-quality services in Kwara State?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: This study utilized a mixed-methods research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The quantitative aspect involves a survey questionnaire administered to ECE teachers, while the qualitative aspect includes semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders such as government officials, ECE policymakers, and community leaders.

Population, Sample and Sampling Techniques: For qualitative part, the population of the study consists of parents/guardians of children enrolled in ECE programs, government officials responsible for education policy, ECE policymakers, and community leaders in Kwara State, Nigeria. For the quantitative part, the population of the study consists of 7,236 ECE teachers in Kwara State, Nigeria. Stratified, purposive and convenience techniques were used to select 20 participants (parent/guardians of enrolled children, ECE administrators and officials of Ministry of Education). In the same vein, Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table was used to determine the sample size of 364. Furthermore, the stratified, purposive and simple random techniques were adopted to select participants in ECE schools across the senatorial zones in Kwara State, Nigeria.

Instrumentation: A modified version of Yusuf, Abdulkareem and Popoola's (2023) interview protocol, dubbed the "Interview Protocol on Early Childhood Education (IPECE)," was used to gather information from participants about their views on the issues and problems related to the caliber of early childhood education programs in Kwara State. In order to gather quantitative data from participants, a structured questionnaire named "Early Childhood Education Questionnaire (ECEQ)" was modified. The questionnaire covers themes on support services offered for Early Childhood Education programs and consists of both closed-ended and Likert-scale items. Also, experts' inputs from the Departments of Early Childhood Education and Educational Management and Counselling from Kwara State University and Al-Hikmah University were taken into consideration to ensure the validity of the interview protocol and questionnaire. This was done to make sure that the survey's questions matched the study's research questions. Lastly, a pilot test was carried out with a small sample of 3 participants for the interview procedure and 50 respondents for the survey, respectively, to ensure the reliability of both the questionnaire and the interview protocol. This makes it possible to address any

doubts, misinterpretations, or problems with the questions, guaranteeing that the final versions of the protocol and questionnaire are unambiguous and simple to read.

Procedure for Data Collection: To maintain anonymity and confidentiality, informed consent was acquired from participants and respondents for the survey and interviews, respectively. The informed permission form also helps the researcher to follow moral principles and norms, putting the participants' privacy and well-being first. The participants were interviewed utilizing an audio tape recorder, jotter, laptop, biro, and digital camera. Depending on the accessibility of the participants, the survey was conducted via phone interviews, in-person meetings, and online platforms (Google Form). To guarantee uniformity, data gathering was carried out with the aid of qualified researchers.

Method of Data Analysis: To obtain deeper insights, a theme analysis was conducted on qualitative data obtained from open-ended interview questions. Additionally, using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS version 22), descriptive statistics (such frequencies and percentages) were used to assess quantitative data. This thorough research design combines qualitative and quantitative viewpoints for a nuanced analysis, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the impact of support services on the quality of ECE programs.

RESULTS

Qualitative Approach

Transcription and data codification are indeed crucial components of qualitative research, especially in studies focusing on complex phenomena such as the impact of support services on the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State, Nigeria. Transcription involves converting audio recordings of interviews into written text, capturing verbal responses, non-verbal cues, and contextual information. This process is essential for capturing rich data and facilitating in-depth analysis. The aim of transcription is to accurately represent the interviews, preserving nuances of speech and meaning. Data codification, on the other hand, involves systematically organizing and categorizing interview data to identify patterns, themes, and insights. This process is crucial for gaining a deeper understanding of the phenomena under study. In the present study, the transcription of interviews with key stakeholders in early childhood education programs in Kwara State produced a 15-page document. This transcription serves as a valuable resource for analysis and interpretation. Similarly, data codification in the study focusing on support services on the quality of early childhood education programs helps to systematically organize interview data from key stakeholders. This process facilitates the identification of patterns and themes that contribute to a deeper understanding of the subject matter. The tables depicting the codes assigned and general themes of the study are given below:

Table 1: Code Assigned to Participants

S/N	Participant	Code Assigned
1	Schools	S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, S7, S8, S9, S10
2	Parents	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5
3	Officials from Ministry of Education	M1, M2, M3, M4, M5

Table 2: General Theme on Support-Services and Quality of ECE Programs in Kwara State, Nigeria

Theme One: Key Support Services for ECE Programs
<p>Teacher Training Infrastructural Service Curriculum Implementation Service Learning Material Service Health and Nutritional Service Psychosocial Service</p>
Theme Two: Availability and Accessibility of Key Support Services
<p>Availability of Support Services Accessibility of Support Services</p>
Impact of Support Services on Quality of ECE Programs
<p>Teachers' well being Increase in Pupils 'Achievement</p>
Theme Three: Challenges Associated with ECE Programs in Kwara State
<p>Inadequate Infrastructure Inadequate Qualified Teachers Inadequate Funding Limited Access</p>

Figure 1: General Model on Impact of Support Services on the Quality of ECE Programs in Kwara State, Nigeria

RESULTS

In view of the interview conducted with the participants, majority of the participants agreed that teacher training, infrastructural, curriculum implementation, learning material, health and nutritional, and psychosocial services are the key support services that are provided for ECE programs in Kwara State. Some of the views of the participants are given below:

According to S1 & S8, they opined that:

I believe that teacher training and professional development are crucial for enhancing the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State. Teachers need continuous training to keep up with the latest teaching methodologies. Curriculum development and implementation play a significant role in ensuring that children receive a well-rounded education. A well-developed curriculum can cater to the diverse needs of children."

The view of S3 is that:

Parent and community involvement are essential for the success of early childhood education programs. When parents are actively involved, children tend to perform better academically and socially. Health and nutrition services are critical for the overall well-being of children in Kwara State. Access to healthcare and nutritious meals can significantly impact a child's ability to learn and thrive. Psychosocial support is vital for

children who may be experiencing emotional or behavioral challenges. Providing a supportive environment can help children develop essential social and emotional skills. Infrastructure and learning materials are fundamental for creating a conducive learning environment. Schools need adequate facilities and resources to support quality education."

P1 and M1 opined that..."Monitoring and evaluation are necessary to assess the effectiveness of early childhood education programs. Regular assessments can help identify areas for improvement and ensure that programs are meeting their goals." S7 is of the view that..."Policy and regulatory support are essential for creating a conducive environment for early childhood education. Clear policies and regulations can help ensure that programs meet quality standards."

The figure below depicts the key support services for ECE programs in Kwara State.

Figure 2: Perception on Key Support Services for ECE programs

The views of participants regarding how availability and accessibility of support services affect the quality of ECE programs are given below:

According to S9..."The availability of support services such as teacher training and professional development can significantly enhance the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State. When teachers are well-trained, they can provide better support to young children." S8 opined that..."Accessibility to support services is crucial. If parents and communities can easily access these services, they are more likely to be involved in their children's education, which can improve the overall quality of ECE programs."

P1 and S7 are of the view that:

"Curriculum development and implementation should be accessible to all ECE programs in Kwara State. A standardized curriculum ensures that all children have access to

quality education. Health and nutrition services should be readily available to children in ECE programs. Access to these services can improve children's overall health and well-being, which can positively impact their learning.'

S4 opined that...Psychosocial support should be easily accessible to children who need it. When children have access to support services, they can better cope with emotional or behavioral challenges, which can improve their overall development."

The view of M1 and P4 are:

"Accessibility to support services is crucial for ensuring that all children in Kwara State have access to quality ECE programs. If these services are not easily accessible, some children may miss out on important educational opportunities. The availability of a standardized curriculum that is accessible to all ECE programs in Kwara State is essential for ensuring consistency and quality in early childhood education. The level of availability and accessibility of health and nutrition services can significantly impact children's health and well-being, which in turn affects their ability to learn effectively in ECE programs."

The view of M2 is that..."The availability of support services is low. However, accessible infrastructure and learning materials are crucial for creating a conducive learning environment in ECE programs. The level of availability of these resources directly affects the quality of education provided."

The figure below shows perceived availability, accessibility and impact of support-services on ECE programs.

Figure 3: Perception on Impact of Support Services on Quality of ECE programs

According to S7, he opined that:

“Parental involvement can be a challenge. Some parents may not be actively engaged in their children's education, which can impact the quality of services provided. Cultural beliefs and practices can also pose challenges. Some communities may have different views on early childhood education, which can affect the implementation of quality programs. Health and nutrition issues can impact the quality of services. Without access to proper health and nutrition services, children's overall well-being and ability to learn may be affected. Lack of government support and policies can hinder the delivery of high-quality services. Without adequate support, ECE providers may struggle to meet standards and provide quality education.”

S1: "Limited funding is a significant challenge for ECE providers. Without adequate resources, it is challenging to maintain high-quality services and meet the diverse needs of young children."

M2: "Monitoring and evaluation processes can be challenging to implement effectively. ECE providers may struggle to assess the quality of their services and identify areas for improvement."

P2: "Limited access to health and nutrition services can be a challenge for ECE providers. Ensuring that all children have access to these services can be difficult, particularly in rural areas."

S7: "Limited availability and accessibility of support services, such as monitoring and evaluation processes, can hinder ECE providers' ability to deliver high-quality services."

S8: "Limited funding is a significant challenge for ECE providers. Without adequate resources, it is challenging to maintain high-quality services and meet the diverse needs of young children."

These views highlight some of the key challenges faced by ECE providers in delivering high-quality services in Kwara State, Nigeria. These challenges include limited funding, difficulties in implementing monitoring and evaluation processes, and limited access to health and nutrition services. Addressing these challenges is crucial for improving the quality of ECE programs and ensuring that all children have access to high-quality early childhood education.

Figure 4: Perception on Challenges Associated with ECE programs

Quantitative Approach

Table 3: Perception on Availability of Key Support Services for ECE Programs

S/N	Item	N	SD	D	A	SA	Remark
1	Health and Nutritional Service	356	14	33	201	108	Agreed
2	Psychosocial Service	356	28	25	191	112	Agreed
3	Learning Material Service	356	11	05	158	182	Agreed
4	Curriculum Service	356	31	18	134	173	Agreed
5	Teaching Service	356	17	32	161	156	Agreed

The table indicates that a majority of participants agree that health and nutritional services are adequate, while a smaller number disagree or strongly disagree with this statement. Also, the table suggests a range of perceptions regarding psychosocial services, learning material service, curriculum service and teaching service with a significant number of participants expressing agreement or strong agreement, but also a notable minority expressing disagreement or strong disagreement.

Table 4: Perception on Quality Support Services for ECE Programs in Kwara State

S/N	Item	N	SD	D	A	SA	Remark
1	Curriculum and Pedagogy	356	09	36	209	101	Agreed
2	Instructional Materials	356	26	21	193	116	Agreed
3	Facilities	356	154	173	21	08	Disagreed
4	Teachers	356	203	114	39	10	Disagreed

The above table suggests high number of participants who agree or strongly agree with the quality of curriculum, pedagogy, and instructional materials is a positive indicator for ECE programs in Kwara State, suggesting that these programs are likely providing a high-quality educational experience for young children. In contrast, high number of participants who strongly disagree with both the quality of teaching and facilities suggests a significant issue or concern in these areas.

Table 5: Perception on Challenges Associated with Support Services for ECE Programs in Kwara State

S/N	Item	N	SD	D	A	SA	Remark
1	Inadequate Qualified Teachers	356	02	14	128	212	Agreed
2	Limited Access	356	12	32	171	151	Agreed
3	Inadequate Funding	356	28	21	181	126	Agreed
4	Inadequate Infrastructure	356	-	19	235	102	Agreed
5	Inadequate Learning Materials	356	-	-	169	187	Agreed

The number of participants who agree or strongly agree that children have limited access to ECE programs also highlights a perceived issue in Kwara State. Limited access can be due to various factors such as geographical location, affordability, and availability of ECE facilities. Also, high number of participants agreed that funding, inadequate access to learning materials and inadequate infrastructure for ECE programs in Kwara State is insufficient.

DISCUSSION

In view of the first research question, which based on key support services that contribute to the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State, Nigeria. Evidence from interviews and survey conducted reveal that access to healthcare services, including regular check-ups and immunizations, is crucial for ensuring the well-being of young children in ECE programs. Results indicate that training and professional development opportunities for teachers are critical for improving teaching practices and staying updated with current trends in early childhood education. In addition, evidence from both methods indicate that psychosocial social service, learning material service and infrastructural service are key services that are needed for

ECE programs. The findings coincide with the study of Ajadi (2021) who found that access to health services, including regular check-ups and vaccinations, positively influenced children's attendance and participation in ECE programs. The study of Yusuf, Abdulkareem and Popoola (2023) highlighted the importance of providing nutritious meals and snacks to children in ECE programs, as it was found to positively impact their health and cognitive development. Ogunkoya (2023) found that parents who were actively involved in their child's education, such as attending parent-teacher meetings and volunteering in school activities, had children who performed better academically and socially.

The second research question was based on how the availability, accessibility and impact of support services affect the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State. Evidence from the interviews conducted reveal that support services, such as learning material, psychosocial and health and nutrition services are available and accessible for children in schools. In contrast, evidence from survey indicate that some of the quality of the support services such as infrastructure and teachers are very low. Ekure (2022) explored the availability and accessibility of early childhood care and education (ECCE) services in Nigeria. The study found that while there has been an increase in the number of ECCE centers in the country, many children still lack access to quality ECCE services, particularly in rural areas. The study of Okunaiya and Olajide (2023) examined the availability and utilization of ECE facilities in Nigeria. Findings indicate that while there is an increase in the number of ECE facilities, many are underutilized due to factors such as location, affordability, and quality of services. Olayonu (2022) assessed the availability and accessibility of ECE. Results revealed that while there is a high availability of ECE centers, many are not accessible to children from marginalized communities, emphasizing the need for inclusive policies. The finding is also in tandem with ecosystem theory, which provides a comprehensive framework that helps us understand how various environmental systems influence an individual's development (Elliott & Davis, 2020).

The third research question of the study was based on challenges faced by early childhood education providers in delivering high-quality services in Kwara State. Evidence from interview and survey reveal that challenges such as limited access, inadequate qualified teachers, and inadequate learning materials hindered ECE programs. Wong et. al. (023) examined the challenges facing early childhood education, including issues related to funding, infrastructure, and teacher quality. The study found that while there has been some progress in expanding access to ECE in Nigeria, significant challenges remain in ensuring quality and equitable access for all children. Von Suchodoletzet. al. (2023) examined an overview of the development of early childhood education, highlighting key milestones and challenges. The study emphasized the need for increased investment in ECE, particularly in terms of funding, infrastructure, and teacher training, to improve the availability and accessibility of ECE services in the country.

CONCLUSION

The study on the impact of support services on the quality of early childhood education (ECE) programs in Nigeria, with a focus on Kwara State, provides valuable insights into the factors that contribute to the effectiveness of ECE programs. Through empirical evidence and participant views, several key findings have emerged. Firstly, the availability and accessibility of support

services, such as teacher training, curriculum development, health and nutrition services, infrastructure, and psychosocial support, play a crucial role in enhancing the quality of ECE programs. These services are essential for creating a conducive learning environment and meeting the diverse needs of young children. Secondly, the level of availability and accessibility of these support services significantly impacts the quality of ECE programs. Limited availability and accessibility can hinder the effectiveness of programs and negatively impact children's learning and development. Thirdly, challenges such as the lack of trained and qualified teachers, limited access to resources, funding constraints, parental involvement, cultural beliefs and practices, and inadequate government support pose significant barriers to delivering high-quality ECE services. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach, including increased investment in ECE, improved teacher training, better infrastructure, and greater community involvement and awareness. In conclusion, the study highlights the importance of support services in enhancing the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria, particularly in Kwara State. By addressing the challenges and ensuring the availability and accessibility of support services, stakeholders can work towards improving the overall quality of early childhood education and promoting the holistic development of young children.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

There is need to enhance teacher training programs to ensure that ECE teachers are well-equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to deliver high-quality education.

Government need to implement strategies to increase parental and community involvement in ECE programs, such as parent education workshops and community outreach programs.

There is need for government to develop and implement a robust and culturally relevant curriculum that meets the needs of young children in Kwara State, with a focus on play-based learning and holistic development.

There is need to ensure that all ECE programs have access to adequate health and nutrition services, including regular health check-ups and nutritious meals for children.

Government must ensure Implement psychosocial support programs for children and families in ECE programs, including counseling services and support groups.

Government and other stakeholders need to Invest in improving infrastructure and providing adequate learning materials in ECE centers to create a conducive learning environment.

Implementation of regular monitoring and evaluation processes to assess the quality and effectiveness of ECE programs, and use the findings to make improvements.

Government need to allocate more funding to ECE programs to ensure that they have the resources needed to provide high-quality education and support services.

REFERENCES

- Adesuyi-Fasuyi, O. (2023). *Preschool STEM Education: Perspectives on the Education-Practice Gap and Professional Development* (Doctoral dissertation, San Francisco State University).
- Agarry, R. O. (2022). Effect of Participatory Training Programme on Early Childhood Education Pre-Service Teachers' Production of Locally-Made Instructional Materials in Kwara State. *Journal of Pedagogy, Andragogy and Heutagogy in Academic Practice*, 3(3), 100-111.
- Aghnaita, A., & Norhikmah, N. Problems of Learning the Qur'an in Early Childhood Education during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Al-Athfal: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak*, 8(2), 117-128.
- Alam, A. T. M., Hasan, M. N., Emon, M. N. I., Akash, R. I., Chowdhury, M. A. B., & Uddin, M. Effect of Children's Socio-Economic and Health Status in Early Childhood Education Programs in Bangladesh: A Cross-Sectional Study of Mics-2019. *Nahidul Islam and Akash, Robiul Islam and Chowdhury, Muhammad Abdul Baker and Uddin, Md, Effect of Children's Socio-Economic and Health Status in Early Childhood Education Programs in Bangladesh: A Cross-Sectional Study of Mics-2019*.
- Ajadi, M. S. (2021). *Assessment of Government Involvement in Establishment of Early Childhood Care Development and Education in Kwara State, Nigeria* (Doctoral dissertation, Kwara State University (Nigeria)).
- Ekure, E. (2021). *Influence of Structural and Process Qualities on Preschoolers' Numeracy Performance in Early Childhood Education Centres in Ilorin East* (Doctoral dissertation, Kwara State University (Nigeria)).
- Elliott, S., & Davis, J. M. (2020). Challenging taken-for-granted ideas in early childhood education: A critique of Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory in the age of post-humanism. *Research handbook on childhood nature: Assemblages of childhood and nature research*, 1119-1154.
- El Zaatari, W., & Maalouf, I. (2022). How the Bronfenbrenner bio-ecological system theory explains the development of students' sense of belonging to school?. *SAGE Open*, 12(4), 21582440221134089.
- D'Souza, S., Stewart, T., Gerritsen, S., Gibbons, A., & Duncan, S. (2023). Preschool behavioural and emotional outcomes associated with participation in early childhood education and care. *Early Education and Development*, 34(1), 228-242.

- Gyekye-Ampofo, M., Opoku-Asare, N. A., & Andoh, G. B. (2023). Early Childhood Care and Education in The 21st Century: A Review of the Literature. *British Journal of Education*, 11(4), 81-95.
- Haq, A. M., & Roesminingsih, E. (2024). Situational Leadership Skills of Foundation Heads in Human Resource Development for Early Childhood Education. *Munaddhomah: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 5(1), 26-40.
- Joo, Y. S., Magnuson, K., Duncan, G. J., Schindler, H. S., Yoshikawa, H., & Ziol-Guest, K. M. (2020). What works in early childhood education programs?: A meta-analysis of preschool enhancement programs. *Early Education and Development*, 31(1), 1-26.
- Kamilu, M. O., Baba, A. O., & Abdulkareem, H. B. (2022). Influence of quality early childhood education centres on social interaction of pre-primary school pupils in Kwara State. *Journal of General Education and Humanities*, 1(3), 139-148.
- Kamiya, Y., & Nomura, M. (2023). Evaluating the impact of early childhood education on child development in Lao PDR. *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 31(1), 10-30.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Sample size determination table. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30, 607-610.
- Lewis, H. R., Lipscomb, S. T., Hatfield, B. E., Jäderholm, C. M., & Tominey, S. L. (2024). Early Childhood Teachers' Relationships with Families When Children Experience Adversity. *Journal of Research in Childhood Education*, 1-26.
- Modise, M. R., Fonsén, E., Heikka, J., Phatudi, N., Bøe, M., & Phala, T. (2023). *Global Perspectives on Leadership in Early Childhood Education* (p. 340). Helsinki University Press.
- Nolan, H. A., & Owen, K. (2024). Medical student experiences of equality, diversity, and inclusion: content analysis of student feedback using Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory. *BMC Medical Education*, 24(1), 55-73.
- Ogunkoya, A. (2023). *Early Childhood Education (ECE) in Nigeria: A system Analysis of Policy in National and Local Contexts* (Doctoral dissertation, University of East London).
- Okunaiya, G. A., & Olajide, S. O. (2023). Assessment of early childhood education programme implementation by pre-schools during covid-19 lockdown in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(7), 30-42.
- Olayonu, O. O. (2021). *Mode of Entry and Attitude as Correlates of Pre-service Teachers' Performance in Early Childhood and Primary Education in Kwara State, Nigeria* (Doctoral dissertation, Kwara State University (Nigeria)).

- Rashid, R., & Akkari, A. (2020). A review of Early Childhood Education (ECE) in Bangladesh: status and impact. *International Journal of Education*, 12(1), 59-74.
- Seymour, S. L. (2023). *An Examination of Early Childhood Care and Education in the Cayman Islands: An Exploration of Early Childhood Educators Developmentally Appropriate Beliefs and Sensitive Caregiving Practices* (Doctoral dissertation, Fielding Graduate University).
- Sosu, E. M., & Pimenta, S. M. (2023). Early childhood education attendance and school readiness in low-and middle-income countries: The moderating role of family socioeconomic status. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 63, 410-423.
- Velandia, E. A., Farr, A., Musso, S., Soto, N., & Fettes, D. L. (2024). Parents' adverse childhood experiences matter too: The impact of multigenerational trauma on participation in early childhood education for Latinx children. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 67, 208-217.
- Von Suchodoletz, A., Lee, D. S., Henry, J., Tamang, S., Premachandra, B., & Yoshikawa, H. (2023). Early childhood education and care quality and associations with child outcomes: A meta-analysis. *Plos one*, 18(5), e0285985.
- Wong, S., Fordham, L., Davis, B., & Tran, D. (2023). Supporting regional and remote children's participation in high quality early years services. *Australasian Journal of Early Childhood*, 48(3), 217-233.
- Yusuf, S., Abdulkareem, H. B., & Popoola, B. O. (2023). The impact of quality early childhood education centers on pre-schoolers' social interaction. *Indonesian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(2), 181-190.

Authors' Biography

Dr. Yusuf Suleiman is a Senior Lecturer in the Department of Educational Management and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Al-Hikmah University, Kwara State, Nigeria and also the Director, Centre for Research, Industrial Linkage and International Cooperation, Al-Hikmah University, Kwara State, Nigeria

Dr. Usman Tunde Saadu is a Senior Lecturer and Head of Department, Early Childhood and Primary Education, Faculty of Education, Kwara State University, Malete, Kwara State, Nigeria.